

Strategies for Minimizing False Positives in Intrusion Detection Systems

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ABSTRACT-During the most recent decade with the development of digital assaults, data wellbeing has become a significant issue everywhere throughout the globe. These Detection Systems are a fundamental component for organizing security frameworks and play a very significant job in distinguishing huge numbers of assaults. In spite of the fact that there are various sorts of interruption identification frameworks, all these frameworks endure a typical issue which is creating a large amount of alarms & an immense number of bogus positives. This downside is becoming the principle inspiration for some exploration papers in this field. The emphasis will be on information mining methods. This paper audits in excess of thirty related examinations during the most recent decade with the expectation of giving a reference to additionally investigate here. A few open issues have likewise been tended to in this paper.

Keywords: Evaluation Metrics, Intrusion Detection Systems, Objective Metric, Performance Metrics.

I. Introduction

During the most recent years, the quantity of unapproved exercises, interruptions and assaults in PC systems has developed broadly [11-15]. With the touchy increment in the number of administrations open via the network, data security of utilizing the network as the media should be cautiously concerned and adequate insurance is required against digital assaults [20-22].

Intrusion Detection System are a basic part of a total safeguarding the so called top to bottom engineering for PC security. IDS is a compelling security innovation, which can recognize, forestall and potentially respond to the assault [16-19].

Fig. 1 shows various groupings of these systems. From the perspective of recognition strategy, IDSs can be separated into two classes:

abnormality and misuse based recognition. Abnormality identification attempts to decide if deviation from the actual use examples can be hailed as interruptions. While, misuse recognition utilizes examples of notable assaults or loopholes of the framework to recognize interruptions [2]. As can be seen in Fig. 1, as the type of source of data be, an IDS may either be host or network based. A host based IDS (HoIDS) investigates occasions, for example, process identifiers and framework calls, mostly identified with various operating system data. While, a network based IDS breaks down system-like occasions: Internet addresses, administration, convention utilization, etc. [3]. Despite the fact that IDS arrangements have been utilized for around more than a decade, a significant issue pending is that these frameworks give immense number of cautions which a large portion of them are bogus alarms or low significance. For instance, even a one IDS sensor can produce a huge

number of alarms in 24 hrs [4,5]. Huge amounts of alarms are difficult to manage and overpowering to us. Assessing a huge number of cautions every day is unfeasible, particularly if 99% of them are bogus cautions [6].

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Fig. 1. Characteristics of IDS

II. Parameters

There are numerous components to assess the IDS, for example, response time, value, asset use, viability, and so forth [1]. The viability of an IDS is assessed by its expectation capacity to give a right grouping of occasions to be assault or typical conduct [4]. As per the genuine idea of a given occasion and the expectation from an IDS, four potential results have appeared in Table 1, which is called as data matrix. Genuine negatives just as obvious positives relate to a right activity of these systems; True negatives are occasions which are really typical and are effectively marked as should be expected, genuine positives are occasions which are in reality assaults and are effectively named as assaults. Individually, bogus positives allude to typical occasions being named assaults; bogus negatives are assault occasions mistakenly named typical occasions.

ReN : Real Negative FIN : Untrue Negative FIP : Untrue Positive ReP: Real Positive

$$\frac{\text{False Positive}}{\text{False Positive} + \text{Real Negative}}$$

Rate of FIP =

$$\frac{\text{False Negative}}{\text{False Negative} + \text{Real Positive}}$$

Rate of True Positive =

$$\frac{\text{Real Positive}}{\text{Real Positive} + \text{False Negative}}$$

Rate of True Negative =

$$\frac{\text{Real Negative}}{\text{Real Negative} + \text{False Positive}}$$

Accuracy =

$$\frac{\text{Real Positive} + \text{Real Negative}}{\text{Real Positive} + \text{Real Negative} + \text{False Negative} + \text{False Positive}}$$

Precision =

These days, the interruption identification framework needs good detection rate and a little bogus caution rate. The significant problems about getting various calculations which are proposed to diminish bogus alerts is that decreasing simply bogus positive rate isn't enough. Some bogus alerts decrease methods will cause low exactness as a result of a few tasks like over speculation, missing genuine assault cautions, and so on. In this way, compelling methods will lessen the bogus types [18-19].

TABLE I CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual Case	Prediction	Type of Case
	Common	Assault
Common	TrN	FIP
Assault	FIN	TrP

III. Various Techniques

Some of the methods that are there in this field are as shown here in this paper. These techniques can be divided into following two types as can be seen the fig 2. Various datasets

Fig. 2. False Positives Reduction Approaches

A. Detection Techniques

In the year 2008, Wu and Ye [5] looked at the precision, location rate, bogus caution rate for some of the assault types which are DS, UR, Probe, RL. They give precision correlation of Discovery and Data Mining Cup 99), D8 (DARPA 1998), D9 (DARPA 1999), D0 (DARPA 2000).

These four sorts of assaults by C4 and S.V.M calculations methods. They show that C4 demonstrates better than S.V.M in precision of Probe, DS and UR assaults recognition; yet in bogus caution rate, S.V.M method is much better. They recommend consolidating the two strategies, with the goal that general precision can be expanded enormously. Various other techniques like Decision Tree Classification is also a good method of detection. In light of worthy degrees of bogus caution rate, choice tree is more appropriate than rule-based for displaying interruption identification frameworks.

TABLE II

DETECTION TECHNIQUES

Researches in year (2000-2011)	False Positive Reduction Techniques	K9	D8	D9	D0	Real world	False Positive Rate
[1]	S.V.M	+					~1%
[4]	C 4	+					~1.45%
[9]	DTC ,RBC	+					~3.2%
[2]	DTC , Bayesian Method	+					Nil
[7]	SOM , K-means Algo.	+				+	~0.90-2.44 %

B. Alerts Processing Techniques

In the year 2000, Clifton and Gengo utilized information mining methods to distinguish arrangements of alerts that imaginable outcome from ordinary conduct, empowering development of channels to dispense with those alerts. They have examined the location of continuous alarm groupings, so as to utilize this information for making IDS ready channels. Other alert systems have been tested as well. For eg: Statistical Filtering is an alert processing technique whose false positive reduction ratio is 75% [8]. While on the other hand, the Self-Organizing Map technique has shown significant results by showing as high as 90% false positive reduction ratio [7]. If we talk about machine learning algorithms that have been tested by various researchers, they haven't proved to be as effective. For eg: Machine-Learning (ALAC) algorithm shows 30% false positive reduction ratio only.

TABLE III

ALERTS PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

Researches in year (2000-2011)	False Positive Reduction Techniques	K9	D8	D9	D0	Real world	False positive reduction ratio
[10]	SAM						Nil
[7],[8]	Clusters					+	~76%, 86%
[2],[1],[7]	Machine Learning , Clusters			+		+	~30.2%, ~50%
[6]	Different Parameters					+	~98%
[4]	Clustering Technique					+	Nil
[9]	Clustering		+				Nil
[1],[5]	Classification , Clustering			+		+	~37.2%
[4],[2]	Clustering , RCA		+	+		+	81%,94%, 75%
[5]	Classify, Clustering					+	82-99%,43 .23%
[8]	Flitering by Stat.			+			~75.3%
[3]	Classify			+			~36.4%
[7]	SOM , K-means Algo.			+		+	89%,88%, 51%

IV. Conclusion

This paper reviewed some of the techniques of decreasing these untrue positives in Intrusion Detection Systems. From the year 2000 to 2011, various techniques have been discussed and the table also shows their rate of effectiveness. While no technique is perfect in reducing the false positives to almost zero but some techniques have proven to be far more effective than the rest. It can't be said that some

techniques are not effective and some are effective because they all use different datasets that have resulted in such variations in the end result. These results could be used by various researchers in future for further looking into the possible changes that can make the bogus alarms to reduce without affecting accuracy. The accuracy factor still remains a promising task for researchers in the future.

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